

The Influence of Contextual Teaching And Learning Models on Learning Outcomes of Class V Students UPTD Sd Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024

Meri Christina Sitanggang^{1*}, Lisbet Novianti Sihombing², Fine Eirene Siahaan³
Universitas HKBP Nomensen Pematang Siantar, Indonesia

Corresponding Author: Meri Christina Sitanggang;
merisitanggang02@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine whether there is an influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model on the learning outcomes of class V students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024. The method in this research is a quantitative experimental type method whose research design is Pre-experimental type one group pretest -posttest. Conducted in September 2023, the population of all students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar and a sample of 28 students consisting of 14 female students and 14 male students used was purposive sampling with two research variables: the dependent variable (x) in the form of learning outcomes, as well as the independent variable (y) in the form of the Contextual Teaching and Learning model, a learning concept that helps teachers link the material taught with students' real world situations which encourages students to make connections between the knowledge they have and its application in their daily lives. Data collection techniques are test techniques with validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differentiating power tests. The test results using the N-gain technique with the help of the SPSS version 21 program, based on the calculation results obtained a mean of 0.6726, that the effectiveness is $0.7 > 0.6726 > 0.3$ which is included in the medium category, in the ANOVA test the significant value is 0.000, which is where $0.000 < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that all independent variables have a significant influence on the dependent variable. So it can be concluded that there is an influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning model on the learning outcomes of class V students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024.

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of a country's civilization is education. Education is one of the foundations for efforts to develop and grow students' potential by encouraging and providing various facilities for the teaching and learning process. Based on Law number 20 of 2003 article 1 (1), explains that education is a place or forum that develops all human potential in order to create and have religious spiritual strength, intelligence, personal personality and the skills needed in himself, his family, society. as well as the nation.

Teachers must choose the most appropriate learning strategies to facilitate the learning process well, with overall methods and procedures that emphasize teaching and learning activities to achieve certain goals (Agus Mukhtar Rosyidi, et al: 2017). A learning model that will help in the ongoing learning process, and must pay attention to the characteristics of each student who is equipped with the model used in the learning process. Student characteristics are very important for teachers to know because they will be used as a reference in formulating the desired teaching strategy (Nevi Septiani, et al: 2020).

In practice, teachers still use monotonous learning methods such as lectures and which are centered on the teacher, some students even become sleepy while following the ongoing learning process. Many students' activities are still just listening to the teacher and taking notes on what is in their textbooks. Students are increasingly less motivated to participate in the learning process, and no students even want to ask questions after completing the learning process.

Seeing the low completion of learning outcomes with data on monthly test scores for science subjects with a KKM of 65, only 27% of students completed, 73% of students did not complete and for Indonesian language subjects with a KKM of 65, only 30% of students completed and 70% of students did not. complete and SBDP subjects with a KKM of 70, only 40% of students completed and 60% did not complete. For this reason, it is necessary to apply the Contextual Teaching and Learning model.

Contextual Teaching and Learning model is a holistic learning process and aims to help students understand teaching material by relating it to the context of their daily lives, so that they have dynamic and flexible knowledge skills to actively construct their own understanding (Lisbet N Sihombing: 2018). This is also reinforced by (Juni Agus Simaremare, et al: 2022) that the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model can increase individual discovery abilities and also make learning conditions that were initially passive become more active and creative. So that teachers can change learning that was initially teaching oriented to student oriented, as well as making it easier to introduce the learning material provided and improving student learning outcomes.

Contextual Teaching and Learning Model is learning that directly involves students in understanding the material and improving thinking and linking this learning to everyday life which can improve student learning outcomes. Specifically on learning 'Animal Movement Organs' in class V UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The conceptual framework is the relationship between one concept and another of the problem to be researched, so a conceptual framework can be prepared for the influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model on the Learning Outcomes of Class V UPTD Students at SD Negeri 12233 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024.

By using the Pretest, where the Pretest is a test carried out before learning or a topic is explained, then the Contextual Teaching and Learning model is applied, which links the subject to students' real life in everyday life, then the posttest is applied which is a test or exam carried out After the learning process has been carried out, then analyze the data with the information that has been obtained during the research to obtain results from the research. So that it can create results from the influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model on learning outcomes.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

The research used is quantitative research. With a pre-Experimental Design type. Where the researcher used a One-group Pretest-Posttest Design. In research, the results of the treatment will be known more accurately because you can compare the conditions before the treatment was given. (Sugiyono: 2018).

Figure 1 One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design

Information:

0 1 = pretest score

0 2 = posttest score

X = treatment given

The population in the research were all students at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, and the sample taken by class V students was 28 students. This research uses a test instrument in the form of multiple choices with the aim of measuring learning outcomes. Before it is used for data collection, the data testing stage uses validity testing, reliability testing, difficulty level testing, and differentiating data testing. In data analysis, the N-gain test and anova test were used.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

In this research, instrument testing was carried out on class V students of UPTD SD Negeri 122345 Jl. Thmrin, the hero of Pematang Siantar, numbering 25 students. The instruments in this research include multiple choice tests to measure student learning outcomes. The instrument trial results data consists of 30 questions. Before conducting the research, a validity test, reliability test, difficulty level test, discrimination test were first carried out, then analyzed the data using the N-gain and anova tests.

Test instrument

1. Validity test

An instrument is said to be valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and if it is not valid then $r_{table} > r_{count}$ of 30 questions. After testing the instrument at another school, there were 20 valid questions and 10 invalid questions, so that what was distributed were questions with a total of 20 valid statements.

2. Reliability Test

The question reliability test aims to see the accuracy of the tool in assessing what it assesses. In this case, observe how each question item is determined in assessing or testing students' abilities and knowledge. Based on the results of the reliability test with the Kr20 model, the correlation coefficient is $0.80 < r_{11} < 1.00$ so the interpretation is included in the high value range. Then it can be concluded that the data is declared reliable.

3. Test Difficulty Level

The difficulty level test is carried out to see the level of difficulty of each question that has been distributed and determine whether the question is too easy or too difficult. that the easy question category has 3 questions (5, 15, 20), the medium question category has 12 questions (1, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19), the There are 5 difficult questions (2, 3, 4, 6, 8).

4. Discriminating Power Test

The test is carried out by computing the coefficient between the scale score distribution itself, which has a classification of the distinguishing power of questions that are very bad, bad, fair, good, or very good. There are 11 questions in the good category, 8 questions in the fair category, and 1 question in the bad category.

Data analysis

5. N-gain test

In this research, Descriptive Statistics is used to assess the influence of the contextual teaching and learning model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, can be seen from the following table:

Table 1 N-Gain Test

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Ngain_score	28	.38	1.00	.6726	.16420
Valid N (listwise)	28				

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the value (Mean) in the trial class shows that the effectiveness of student learning outcomes is 0.6726. It can be concluded that the effectiveness is $0.7 > 0.6726 > 0.3$, which means the results are in the medium category .

6. Anova test

In this study, One Why Anova was used to see the significance of differences between the averages of different groups in one or more respondent variables in the population using the Contextual Teaching and Learning model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, which can be seen in the table. under

Table 2 Anova test

ANOVA					
Learning outcomes					
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	19687,500	1	19687,500	240,643	,000
Within Groups	4417.857	54	81,812		
Total	24105.357	55			

In the significance results of the anova test, it is 0.000, which means the significant value is $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means there is an influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar students.

Discussion

This research was carried out at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar on theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs in class V. Before conducting research, you must first test the instrument at another school, namely UPTD SD Negeri 122345 JL Thamrin, Pahlawan to prove that the questions are suitable for use. There were 30 questions distributed to 25 students at UPTD and then the results of these questions would be tested on the instrument. The tests carried out are validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and questions of differentiability tests. After the data is valid and reliable, the number of questions declared valid will be tested on the UPTD research class at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

Then the researcher conducted research at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar, the researcher conducted a pretest before being treated with the Contextual Teaching and Learning model and a posttest after being given treatment at the research school. The pretest was carried out to see the condition of the students' initial abilities before giving treatment to the students at the UPTD. After the pretest, the average score was below the KKM, then after carrying out the pretest the researcher provided material with the theme 1 Animal and Human Movement Organs using the Contextual Teaching and Learning model , After the treatment was carried out, the researcher gave a posttest, namely a final test to see the students' abilities after being given the model.

Based on data that has been tested by researchers through the SPSS 21 test, it can be concluded that the average score of the 28 students in the pretest and posttest results is 45, 36 and 82, 86 based on the score data before and after the treatment has increased. After carrying out descriptive tests, the researcher also carried out data analysis tests, namely the N - Gain and Anova tests. In the N- Gain test, the value (Mean) was seen to be 0.6726, that the effectiveness was

$0.7 > 0.6726 > 0.3$, which is the result. falls into the medium category. In the ANOVA test, the significant value is 0.00, where $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, then there is an influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning Model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

Based on the presentation of the N-Gain test results, it can be concluded that the influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning model has a positive and significant effect on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar T.A 2023/2024.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the problem formulation and hypothesis proposed as well as the research results obtained and then discussed, it can be concluded that the research conducted at UPTD SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar by conducting one group pretest-posttest had an influence on student learning outcomes. This is measured from the results of the students' average score which was originally 45.36 and after being given the Contextual Teaching and Learning model treatment it rose to 82.86.

In the N-gain test, the effectiveness of the data obtained was $0.7 > 0.6726 > 0.3$, where the results fell into the medium category. Next, an Anova test is carried out using the specified criteria, if $F < 0.05$ is significant then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, if $F > 0.05$ then H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected, from the significance data there is 0.000 so it is said that $F < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$). So H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that all independent variables have a significant influence on the dependent variable. This explanation shows that there is an influence of the Contextual Teaching and Learning model on the learning outcomes of class V UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar.

FURTHER STUDY

With research limited to variables, researchers recommends that similar research be conducted targeting different variables different groups or contexts. As a result, adding mediating variables can. It can also be studied by future researchers to gain new insight into this matter relationship between variables. The results of this research can help future researchers identify what improvements the company can make in order to improve their operations to be more sustainable and able to face change. The recommendations above will help researchers to identify what factors have a significant influence.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

So further lessons that can be given to make it better in the future are:

- a. Advice for teachers

In the learning process, teachers should teach by applying discovery learning so that all students can be active in participating in the learning process, and teachers give students the freedom to relate the material studied to the students' real lives, so that it is not always centered on the teacher but also on the students.

b. Suggestions for schools

To the school to always motivate teachers to be able to use the Contextual Teaching and Learning model in the learning process

c. Advice for students

To UPTD students at SD Negeri 122337 Pematang Siantar to be more active in studying and enthusiastic in participating in the learning process, because with this students will better understand the explanation given by the teacher so that it can help improve learning outcomes.

d. Suggestions for researchers

This research is the basis for developing one's potential in knowing interesting models so that researchers can apply them in the future when they enter the field. And it is hoped that it can develop the Contextual Teaching and Learning model in depth

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